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Appeal to ridicule: "COVIDIOT"

Domina Petric, MD

Urban Dictionary coined the word "covidiot" to describe "someone who ignores the warnings regarding public health or safety" or "a person who hoards goods, denying them from neighbors." I agree that we must all behave very responsible during the COVID-19 crisis, but mockery is the last thing we need now. Idiot mocks, smart people give advice!

Urban Dictionary¹ coined the word "covidiot" to describe "someone who ignores the warnings regarding public health or safety" or "a person who hoards goods, denying them from neighbors."

This is a classical appeal to ridicule logical fallacy. Instead of giving a useful advice and valid arguments to people who are not able to cope with COVID-19 pandemic, the so called "you'reandidiot" coined this ridicule neologism that is now spreading internet faster than the virus SARS-CoV-2.

Mockery is the last thing we need in the COVID-19 pandemic.

Both COVID-19 pandemic and mental health issues caused by this crisis are very important topics for scientific discussion.

Moukadam N (MD, PhD) and Shah A (MD) explained that COVID-19 is now affecting more than 27 countries, raising concerns of widespread panic and increasing anxiety in individuals subjected

to the (real or perceived) threat of the virus. Media coverage has highlighted COVID-19 as a unique threat, rather than one of many, which has added to panic, stress, and the potential for hysteria².

Therefore, mass media are partly responsible for the irresponsible behavior of some people.

Professor David Forbes³ (University of Melbourne, Australia) explained that "Coronavirus isn't only taking a physical toll, it's playing with our minds, too."

I agree that we must all behave very responsible during the COVID-19 crisis, but mockery is the last thing we need now.

Idiot mocks, smart people give advice!

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